

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Training and evaluation materials

Deliverable D6.1

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This deliverable is a preliminary version that will be updated as a result of the different rounds of pilots and once TAIS have been defined.

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Del. 6.1 Training and evaluation material [January 2020]

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RAISD Glossary

AB	Advisory Board
ARU	Action Research Unit
ARUL	ARU Leader
CA	Consortium Agreement
CoU	Community of Users
CRIOS	Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software tool
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FD	Forced Displacement
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
GA	Grant Agreement
GRASIA	Research Group on Agent-based, Social & Interdisciplinary Applications (Spanish: GRupo de investigación en Aplicaciones Sociales e Interdisciplinarias basadas en Agentes)
GUNI	Global University - Network of Innovation
HEIW	Higher Education in the World
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	IP Rule
IS	Information Service
JCR	Journal Citation Reports
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LERU	League of European Research Universities
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
R&I	Research and Innovation
REPAC	Research Ethics Policy and Advisory Committee
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SC	Steering Committee
SDG	UN's Sustainable Development Goal
SO	Specific Objective
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UN	United Nations
UNCHR UN	High Commissioner for Refugees
UNRWA	United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package

About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

1. RAISD Overview

RAISD aims at identifying vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people, their specific challenges and needs, to provide them tailored attention and inclusion strategies.

Objectives:

- Discover highly vulnerable groups among Forcibly Displaced People.
- Develop the novel concept of vulnerability context to gain a different perspective in dealing with migration.
- Analyse their specific challenges and needs regarding integration and well-being.
- Identify suitable and evidence-based aid strategies to promote their involvement and improve their inclusion in host societies.

Research strategies:

- Combine methodological triangulation of Responsible Research and Innovation, action research, and socio-ecological models.
- Monitor inclusion measures for vulnerable migrants developing innovative standard methods (Collaborative Research and Innovation Online tool).
- Co-design actions transversely integrating the gender perspective and supporting sustainability.
- Integration of Social and Computer Sciences research.

Innovative Results:

- **Vulnerability Contexts.** The treatment of phenomena related to VGs in FD requires understanding the context where they happen. This context involves three components. First, the people of the VG, with their vital trajectories, contexts of departure, and individual vicissitudes. Second, the host environments and their societies, with their history, culture, socio-economic situation, civil society, and attitudes towards FDP and VGs. Third, the interactions between the previous two elements.
- **TAIS Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies.** Strategies are innovative as they define effective practices (i.e. highly scored by criteria) for a given context describing the correspondence between Vulnerability Contexts, implemented practices and criteria for their evaluation. Just as example, In terms of, for example, target group, objectives, requirements, type of host community, actual results, related artefacts and evaluation by actors.
- **CRIOS collaborative research and innovation online software tool.** The state-of-the-art platform integrates functionality for information and knowledge sharing by different actors involved in the research project, and the related analysis tools that will be fully free/open source software and use open standards and protocols to facilitate interoperability.
- **Ensure the adoption of innovative policy and practices** to address new challenges in the field of migration.

2. Partners, ARUs' details

Partner	Registered name	Address of ARU	Official Contact
P1 UCM	ARU	Av. Séneca, 2, 28040 Madrid, Spain	ngcastillo@pdi.ucm.es cguillo@ucm.es
P2 CESIE	Competence Cell	Via Roma 94, 90133 Palermo, Italy	research@cesie.org
P4 UH	ARU	PL 54 (Unioninkatu 37) 00014 Finland	antti.kivijarvi@helsinki.fi
P5 MENEDEK	ARU	1081 Budapest, Népszínház street 16. III/3, Hungary	andras.kovats@menedek.hu bela.soltesz@menedek.hu
P6 AU	ARU	Yeşiltepe, Yunus Emre Kampüsü, 26470 Tepebaşı/Eskişehir, Turkey	enorhon@anadolu.edu.tr
P7 YU	ARU	Yarmouk University, Irbid, Jordan	refuge@yu.edu.jo
P8 LIU	ARU	Mouseitbeh - PO Box: 146404 Mazraa, Beirut, Lebanon	anwar.kawtharani@liu.edu.lb

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For further information:

- Research and results oriented questions: info@raisd-h2020.eu
- Communication and outreach related matters: press@raisd-h2020.eu

3. The objectives of RAISD

Specific Objective	Results
SO1. Definition and identification of Vulnerability Contexts (VCs)	R1.1. Characterisation of the concept of VC: features and relationships R1.2. Catalogue of VCs linked to the EU
SO2. Identification of attention and inclusion practices for VGs of FDP	R2.1. Catalogue of current attention and inclusion practices related to VGs of FDP
SO3. Identification of key criteria to evaluate strategies and practices for attention and inclusion of VGs of FDP	R3.1. Catalogue of actor-oriented criteria to evaluate strategies and practices for the attention and inclusion of VGs of FDP R3.2. Preliminary study of approaches to integrate actor-oriented criteria in the evaluation of strategies and practices for the attention and inclusion of VGs of FDP
SO4. Mapping among VCs and practices according to evaluation criteria	R4.1. Mapping among vulnerability contexts and practices according to evaluation criteria to define TAISs
SO5. Elaboration of recommendations to develop attention and inclusion strategies tailored to VCs	R5.1. Methodology to elaborate TAISs R5.2. Policy recommendations for effective TAISs for VGs of FDP
SO6. Validation of TAISs and their methodology through pilots	R6.1. Validation of the catalogue of TAISs R6.2. Validation of the methodology to elaborate TAISs
SO7. Development of the Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software tool (CRIOS)	R7.1. CRIOS R7.2. Actor-oriented clients for the CRIOS R7.3. Integration of analysis tools with the CRIOS
SO8. Creation of the observatory for TAISs in FDs	R8.1. Observatory for TAISs in FDs. R8.2. Funding strategies for the observatory of TAISs in FDs

4. Objectives of the ARU's training

The ARU training process relies under the T6.2 of the RAISD project. It entails the training of local stakeholders to carry out the project activities, and their actual execution. More specifically:

T6.2 will provide specific training on the methodological framework, the work and TAIS methodologies (depending on the stage of the project), and the related resources. The targets of this training will be the ARU members and related stakeholders. This task includes for each ARU:

- Identifying interested stakeholders outside the consortium.
- Identifying training needs.
- Preparing training and evaluation materials (D6.1) through collaboration with relevant WP leaders (already involved in the task) and ARU members. Some training material can be shared among ARUs, but partners will pay attention to the specificities of the local context.
- Delivering training.
- Evaluating results of training to establish whether goals have been met.

UNIMED will coordinate the operations; verify training materials and fulfilment of training goals.

A training needs analysis will be carried out among the relevant stakeholders of the process in order to properly design the syllabus of the blended training path. This entails defining an information collection methodology, to collect and process the relevant information and then to design the training path.

A proper consolidated training evaluation methodology will be used to evaluate the training path, including an ex ante analysis, an on-going evaluation and an ex-post evaluation from both trainers and trainees, in order to collect relevant inputs on the effectiveness of the training which will be used to improve its quality in future editions.

5. Training from RAISD members to local stakeholders (ARU members)

Intensive training is needed for institutions' staff on issues concerning RAISD to become familiar with the procedures and methodologies identified by the project. In this regard, local stakeholders need to be trained on the following topics in order to be able to comply with RAISD approach and fulfil the ARUs activities:

- Methodological triangulation;
- RRI, Responsible research and innovation is an approach that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to research and innovation, with the aim to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation (<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>);
- PAR, Participatory action research approach principles;
- SEM, Socio-ecological models;
- Specific training on gender related aspects;

6. Training from local stakeholders (ARU members) to RAISD members

Local stakeholders represent a crucial added value and they will be required to train RAISD members on the determined activities on the basis of TAIs definition. This will produce an effective cooperation framework among the stakeholders, and the identification of mutual priority cooperation areas.

This action will be tailored per each ARU according to involved stakeholders' specificities and only once TAIs have been defined.

A first set of topics can be summarized as follows:

- Training in ethical decision making;
- Training on intercultural dialogue and cultural mediation;
- How to deal with traumatised subjects;
- International and national regulations and conventions on the status of refugees, asylum seekers, migrants.

7. Circular training among local stakeholders (ARU members) and RAISD members

Training materials will be designed and performed in order to be transferrable from one ARU to another for the benefit of all ARU members and vice versa.

An online training platform will be designed and implemented using a popular open-source e-learning platform (such as Moodle). Subsequently the online component of the syllabus is implemented by recording the online modules and uploading them to the online platform in the form of MOOCs.

All MOOCs will be implemented as Open Educational Resources (OERs) covered by Creative Commons (CC) licenses allowing all interested actors to use, re-use and modify the published contents.

Pursuing the goal of transferability across partners the MOOCs will be delivered in English. If some partners are interested in translating the contents in their own national language (for example by adding subtitles to the videos) at their own costs.

8. Training expected results: TAIS implementation and policy recommendations

Once knowledge has been transferred from one ARU to another for the benefit of all ARU members and vice versa, ARU members will be ready to implement a TAIS.

> *First step: What is a TAISs?*

TAIS is the acronym for *Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies*, that RAISD consortium widely mapped vulnerability contexts and practices according to evaluation criteria to define TAISs and defined a proper methodology to elaborate TAISs respectively in WP4 and WP5.

>> *Second step: piloting a TAISs*

The network of ARUs that the project partners will set up, will also allow the validation and assessment of the recommended practices. Each unit will carry out a pilot in the context of WP6 as part the action research strategy. This makes a total of 7 pilots, one in each country. The pilots will follow the guidelines of action research strategy, where investigation and action take rounds (iterations). This permits a better adjustment of future activities through feedback. In the pilots, the ARUs will implement mainly workshops that include the simulation of TAIS with the stakeholders, and the elicitation of their feedback. These stakeholders must represent all the relevant societal actors, as the objective is to come up with sustainable, yet efficient solutions, where the systemic function goal is a balance between resilience and efficiency. The workshops will be at least one full day activities.

>>> *Third step: modifying a TAISs according to stakeholders' feedback*

When the units implement the recommended practices in the pilots, these will provide feedback to validate the previous results in terms of whether the criteria provided a real assessment of the actors' interests, the practices could be applied in the VC, and the results obtained were those expected. This experience will be used in the development and evaluation of the methodology and guidelines.

>>>> *Fourth step: define policy recommendations*

TAISs implementation will lead towards the production of useful outputs in terms of evidence-based policy recommendations as well as a strong capacity building where skills and knowledge will be shared across the ARU members. Thus, TAIs outputs will be fully relevant to the priorities set out by the call for proposals and we can say that they even broaden its scope. In order to guarantee a high level of impact, which is one of the typical potential weaknesses of this type of action (what we call the risk of “writing for the shelf”) and in compliance with a specific need defined in the call text, in addition to and in conjunction with the traditional dissemination effort foreseen in all international project, a specifically designed advocacy action will be carried out to achieve the above mentioned objective. The impact of such an action will be negligible if the results in terms of evidence-based policy recommendations are not taken up by the relevant policy makers, namely at the national level the involved ministries and at the international level the European Institutions. To this purpose, the methodology foresees a strong dissemination action which includes an advocacy dimension which has the goal of raising the attention of these institutions and facilitating the take-up of the project’s results.

ARU recommendations are directed to researchers and institutions to draw their attention on the TAISs arising challenges and how to tackle them, with the scope of supporting their process of definition of actions. The rationale is to support institutions with recommendations for effective and successful research/practical actions.

ANNEX I: Training module syllabus

Title of module:	
Responsible for Module:	
Module Description	
1. Goals	
2. Course Contents	
3. Description of Teaching Methodology	
4. Condition for Participation	
5. Effort	
Contact hours:	
Hours preparation and post processing:	
Total:	
6. Duration of Module	
7. Number of Participants	
8. Inscription Formalities	
9. Literature, Scripts	
<u>Literature:</u>	

ANNEX II: Training report

ARU members training Report

Title of the module	
Places and dates:	
Trainers:	
Learning outcomes:	
The following competencies were taught by introductory inputs and practical exercises:	
At the end of the training workshop, the trainees are expected to be more aware on	

ANNEX III: Ex post training evaluation

Responsible partner:

Location:

Date:

LOGISTIC and ORGANISATION					
<i>[Please answer the following questions by rating on the available choices]</i>	Not at all	A little	Average	Yes	Very
Are you satisfied with the overall logistics of the training?					
Are you satisfied with the infrastructures and facilities provided?					
Do you think that the materials distributed were helpful?					
Was the organization of the training satisfactory (timelines, sequence of courses, etc.)?					
Do you have any comments/suggestions?					

TRAINING					
<i>[Please answer the following questions by rating on the available choices]</i>	Not at all	A little	Average	Yes	Very
Are you satisfied with the quality of the training?					
Do you think that the trainers were well prepared and able to answer any questions?					
How do you assess the impact of this training on your activities?					
Do you think that the training helped you to strengthen your knowledge and skills?					
Have your expectations about the training been satisfied?					
Do you think to share the skills acquired with colleagues at your university?					

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Were the trainers generally available?					
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TRAINING MODULES					
<i>[Please answer the following questions by rating on the available choices]</i>	Not at all	A little	Average	Yes	Very
Do you think that the training's mission is accomplished?					
What is your overall level of satisfaction?					
Are you satisfied with the quality of the training?					

Name at least three things of the training that you found particularly useful
1.
2.
3.
Is there anything you want to add? (Suggestions, proposals, general comments, etc.)